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Capturing Ecology: A Brief Report of Faunistic Diversity at Daytime in a Sport Complex

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ABSTRACT

Ecological photography is the term for pictures taken of the outside world for artistic, scientific, or monitoring objectives. This study aimed to capture the fauna encountered at the M.K.O. Abiola sport complex during the daytime. Capturing was done across all the sections of the sports complex using a smart phone (Apple iPhone 12 Pro Max). The fauna captured can be grouped into invertebrate and vertebrate organisms, which be further divided in to classes such as Insecta (Ants, Grasshoppers, Butterfly, Dragon fly, Beetles, Flies, Bee, Wasps), Arachnida (Spider), Mollusca (African giant land snail), Reptilia (Lizards and Skinks), Aves (Pigeons, Laughing doves, Cattle egrets, Domestic Chickens) and Mammalia (Domestic Goats). The variety of animal species observed during the day in sports complexes showcases the ability of these urban areas to foster biodiversity, even with significant human presence. Insects and birds constitute the bulk of the species that flourish in these settings. Effective management and the integration of biodiversity-friendly methods can improve the ecological significance of sports complexes, aiding in the sustainability of urban ecosystems.

Keywords: Ecological photography, Faunistic Diversity, Insecta, Arachnida, Mollusca, Aves, Mammalia

1. INTRODUCTION

Ecological studies aimed at documenting faunistic diversity in urban landscapes, including sports complexes, are vital for understanding the interaction between wildlife and human-modified environments (Umoren and Idowu, 2024). Sports complexes, with their large

open fields, diverse vegetation, and water sources, can support a variety of faunal species, including birds, insects, reptiles, and small mammals (Aronson et al., 2017). Daytime faunal surveys provide a snapshot of active diurnal species and can help in assessing biodiversity, ecological health, and the impact of urbanization on local ecosystems.

Sports complexes, although constructed primarily for human recreation, have been observed to act as microhabitats for a range of faunal species. The management of these areas, such as maintenance of lawns, planting of ornamental plants, and occasional presence of water bodies, creates a conducive environment for certain species to thrive. Studies conducted in various parts of the world highlight the role of urban green spaces, including sports complexes, in maintaining local biodiversity and offering shelter and resources for urban wildlife (Hall et al., 2016). Daytime surveys typically focus on diurnal species, meaning they are active during the day. Birds are often the most visible and dominant faunal group observed during the day in sports complexes due to their mobility, diversity, and adaptability to urban settings (González-Oreja, 2017). Common bird species that may be observed include pigeons, sparrows, swallows, and sometimes raptors. Insect diversity, including butterflies, bees, and ants, is also prominent in these settings, especially in areas with flowering plants and lawns (Díaz et al., 2016).

Small reptiles such as lizards, as well as mammals like squirrels, can also be found in sports complexes during the day. These species utilize the vegetation and the relatively undisturbed environments in and around the sports fields for foraging and shelter. Studies have shown that urban green spaces, when properly managed, can support a considerable level of biodiversity, even in densely populated areas (Beninde et al., 2015).

The presence of faunal diversity in sports complexes highlights the ecological value of these urban green spaces. Even in areas with heavy human activity, wildlife can find niches where they can thrive. This not only enhances biodiversity but also provides ecosystem services such as pollination, pest control, and seed dispersal (Aronson et al., 2017). Urban wildlife also plays a role in maintaining the ecological balance, contributing to the overall health of the ecosystem. Moreover, documenting faunistic diversity in urban sports complexes contributes to our understanding of species adaptation to urban environments. Some species can cope with and even benefit from the modified landscapes, while others may be sensitive to human disturbances (Umoren, 2024). Continuous monitoring of these faunal populations can help in assessing the sustainability of urban ecosystems and in guiding future urban planning and biodiversity conservation efforts (Hall et al., 2016). While sports complexes provide habitat for certain species, they are not without challenges. Regular human activities, maintenance practices, and urban pollutants can negatively impact faunal populations. For example, the use of pesticides and herbicides for lawn and weed maintenance may reduce insect populations, which are crucial food sources for birds and other wildlife (Chace & Walsh, 2017; Umoren et al., 2025). Additionally, noise and human movement can disturb wildlife, potentially limiting the diversity and abundance of species present during the daytime (Lepczyk et al., 2017). The survey focus on photo-capturing fauna during daytime at the M.K.O. Abiola sport complex.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study Area

The study was carried out in the whole vicinity of M.K.O Abiola International Stadium, (Figure 1), located in Abeokuta, the capital of Ogun State, South-Western Nigeria, is a

prominent multi-purpose sports facility named in honor of Chief Moshood Kashimawo Olawale Abiola (M.K.O. Abiola), a Nigerian business magnate, philanthropist, and political figure. The stadium, designed to meet international standards, has served as a hub for various sporting activities and events, including football, athletics, and other community-based events (Omole, 2018).

Figure 1. GPS Image of the Study Area

2. 2. Capturing of Encountered Animals

The capturing of animals was done across all the sections of the sport complex using a smart phone (Apple iPhone 12 Pro Max: Specification- Triple, 12 MP, f/1.6, 26 mm (wide), 1.7 μm , dual pixel PDAF, sensor-shift OIS; 12 MP, f/2.2, 65mm (telephoto), 1/3.4", 1.0 μm , PDAF, OIS, 2.5 \times optical zoom; 12 MP, f/2.4, 13 mm, 120 $^\circ$ (ultrawide), 1/3.6" TOF 3D LiDAR scanner (depth). Features- Dual-LED dual-tone flash, HDR (photo/panorama) for the duration of fourteen days (2 weeks). A representative of each organism captured was documented.

3. RESULTS

3. 1. Photo-Captured fauna during survey

The photo-captured animals during the survey are presented in Plates 1 – 15 (APPENDIX), the animals represent both invertebrates and vertebrates.

They include

- Class: Insecta (Ants, Grasshoppers, Butterflies, Dragonfly, Beetles, Flies, Bee, Wasps)
- Class: Mollusca (African giant land snail),
- Class: Reptilia (Lizards and Skinks),
- Class: Aves (Pigeons, Laughing doves, Cattle egrets, Domestic Chickens),
- Class: Mammalia (Domestic Goats)

4. CONCLUSIONS

The study gives a brief report of the faunas at the M.K.O. Abiola sport complex during the daytime using photography. Maximize the ecological benefits of sports complexes, it is essential to adopt sustainable landscaping practices, such as planting native species, reducing chemical use, and providing areas of natural vegetation that can serve as refuges for wildlife. The faunistic diversity observed during the daytime in sports complexes reflects the potential of these urban spaces to support biodiversity despite heavy human activity. Insects and birds make up the majority of species that thrive in these environments. Proper management and the incorporation of biodiversity-friendly practices can enhance the ecological value of sports complexes, contributing to the sustainability of urban ecosystems. Future research and monitoring are necessary to fully understand the impact of these spaces on local biodiversity (day and night time) and to develop strategies for optimizing their ecological function.

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APPENDIX

Plate 1. Doryline Ants.

Plate 2. Dragonflies.

Plate 3. Grasshopper.

Plate 4. Butterflies.

Plate 5. Beetles.

Plate 6: Bee

Plate 7: Wasp

Plate 8: Flies

Plate 9: Spider

Plate 10: Moth

Plate 11: Millipede

Plate 12: African giant land snail

Plate 13. Lizard and Skink.

Plate 14. Pigeon, Laughing dove, cattle egret and domestic Hen.

Plate 15. Domestic Goats.